

Assessing the Impact of Measurement Error on Dual-System Estimation: Insights from the 2020 U.S. Census and Post-Enumeration Survey Data¹

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Abstract

The paper investigates the effect of measurement error on dual-system estimation (DSE). It delves into the disagreement between two independent measurements, particularly focusing on the 2020 U.S. Decennial Census and PES (Post-Enumeration Survey) data. The models underlying dual-system estimation often require characteristics to be reported similarly across two independent measurements. This paper examines the stability of demographic characteristics over two repeated measurements and explores how inconsistency of demographic characteristics can bias population estimates. Through simulations, the paper analyzes the sensitivity of population size estimates to varying levels of measurement error, shedding light on the potential bias introduced by measurement discrepancies. The findings underscore the significance of minimizing and reporting measurement error when producing dual-system estimates.

Key Words: Measurement Error, Census, Coverage, Dual-System Estimation, Capture-Recapture

1. Introduction

Dual-System Estimation (DSE) is a popular method for estimating population sizes and measuring census coverage error. However, the accuracy of DSE hinges on the assumption of unbiased measurements, which may be compromised by measurement error. This paper examines the disagreement of demographic characteristics between the 2020 Census and Post-Enumeration Survey and discusses how these inconsistencies might bias estimates of population size.

The impetus for this research lies in the critical need to understand the influence of measurement error on DSE and its ramifications for accurate population estimates. By analyzing the agreement of demographic characteristics across two repeated measurements, this paper investigates the relationship between measurement error and the accuracy of population estimates. Through simulations, the study evaluates how varying levels of measurement error influence potential biases of population size estimates.

The subsequent sections of this paper will address the prevalence of disagreement in measurements, the impact of measurement error, an analysis of specific subgroups, simulation results, and conclude with a summary of findings and implications for future research.

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2. Background

2.1 Quantifying Inconsistency of Measurements

There are numerous ways to quantify the degree of inconsistency between two measurements. This report focuses on Aggregate Difference Rates and the Aggregate Index of Inconsistency for demographic questions, statistics commonly used in prior reports on census content error. For more information on these measures and estimates of disagreement of demographic characteristics between the census and a content reinterview see Singer and Ennis (2000) and Dusch and Meier (2010).

Singer and Ennis (2000) reported low inconsistency for questions regarding sex, age, Hispanic origin, household size, and tenure for Census 2000, while questions about race showed moderate inconsistency. Dusch and Meier (2010) found gross difference rates (GDRs) between 1% and 6%, with notable differences between self-response and enumerator returns - enumerator returns usually showing greater differences. Despite low levels of inconsistency for most demographic groups, some race groups exhibited moderate to high inconsistency.

Similar to our study, Farber (2000) compared census responses to PES responses. Using Census 2000 and the corresponding PES responses, Farber reported that “overall, the rates of inconsistency for the matched cases were about 5 percent or lower.” He also found that “inconsistency appeared to be correlated with coverage” and “increased with more detailed cross classifications.”

2.2 Dual-System Estimation

Capture-recapture studies are often performed to estimate the size of a population. For human populations, these methods have been modified to estimate the number of people in a closed population (Hogan, 2003). The U.S. Census Bureau has been using Dual-System Estimation to estimate the coverage of the decennial census counts since 1980.

In 1980, 1990, and 2000, post-enumeration surveys used post-stratified Petersen estimators to estimate the size of the U.S. population. For the 2010 and 2020 post-enumeration surveys, logistic regression models estimated correct enumeration and match rates (Mule, 2010). These estimators are similar in that they all multiply an estimate of the number of correct enumerations in the census by a weight accounting for census undercoverage. A survey of the census enumerations, called the E-sample, is used to estimate the correct enumeration rate while the PES is used to estimate the census coverage rate.

Because the E sample is selected from the census, the estimated correct enumeration rate is based on census responses. Conversely, the census coverage rate is based on PES-reported characteristics. Thus, the DSE for a specific demographic group is formulated as,

$$\widehat{DSE}_X = \frac{\widehat{CE}_{X1=D}}{\widehat{M}_{X2=D} / \widehat{P}_{X2=D}}$$

Where

$\widehat{CE}_{X1=D}$ is the estimated total number of census correct enumerations who reported being in domain X in the census,

$\widehat{M}_{X2=D}$ is the estimated total number of PES records that matched to the census and reported being in domain X in the PES,

$\widehat{P}_{X2=D}$ is the estimated total number of PES records who reported being in domain X in the PES

The following confusion matrix illustrates how characteristics might be measured differently and what numbers go into the DSE. To emphasize that domain membership may be measured differently between the Census and PES, we call X1 the census measurement of characteristic X, and X2 the PES measurement of X. It should be noted that X1 and X2 might be different from the true value,

denoted T. Additionally, in this table, we assume that all erroneous enumerations (such as duplicates and deceased people) have been removed from both the census and PES.

Table 1: Example of Observed Table from a Post-Enumeration Survey (PES) with Measurement Error

Observed		In PES		Out of PES	Census Total
		X2 = 0	X2 = 1		
In Census	X1 = 0	A	B	C	A+B+C
	X1 = 1	D	E	F	D+E+F
Out of Census		G	H	I	G + H+I
PES Total		A+D+G	B+E+H	C+F+I	N

In this table, the cells in light grey are unknown. The DSE is an estimate of N. We wish to estimate the DSE for two domains $X = 0$ and $X = 1$. For $X = 0$, the DSE would be,

$$\widehat{DSE}_{X=0} = \frac{A + B + C}{A + D / A + D + G}$$

And the DSE for $X = 1$ would be,

$$\widehat{DSE}_{X=1} = \frac{D + E + F}{B + E / B + E + H}$$

The PES strives to replicate the census demographic questions as closely as possible, using identical wording and reference dates. However, differences remain; the PES interviews typically occur several weeks or months after the census enumerations, even though the reference date of April 1 is clearly stated in the PES Interview. Additionally, PES interviews are mostly conducted by an interviewer; while the census interviews are often done by self-response.

3. Methods

3.1 Prevalence of Disagreement

To support our analysis, we first tabulated unweighted confusion matrices using the E and P samples. Confusion matrices show the observed results of matching and characteristic measurement. A key requirement of dual-system estimation is the removal of spurious records before performing estimation (Wolter, 1986). Accordingly, erroneous enumerations and out-of-scope records (e.g., people living outside the country, in Remote Alaska Areas, or in group quarters) were removed before creating the confusion matrices.

Since the goal is to explore differences between these two surveys and their impact on estimates, we conducted our analysis on unweighted data. This approach aims to analyze our sample rather than make inferences about the general population. It should be noted that because of oversampling and nonresponse, the unweighted sample counts in the appendix are not representative of the general population.

The four cells in the upper left quadrant of each confusion matrix show how the matching records were classified in both systems. It is this quadrant that is used to calculate difference rates and the index of inconsistency. Appendix B in Singer and Ennis (2000) contains an elegant example of how aggregate difference rates and indexes of inconsistency are calculated.

3.2 Effect on Dual-System Estimation

To explore the effect of measurement error on dual-system estimation, we first created a framework with 10 parameters that could be changed to explore how DSEs increase or decrease as the

parameters change. We then wrote the DSE in terms of these parameters and used algebra or simulations to analyze the DSE bias under common capture models.

3.2.1 Framework

Our framework to explore measurement error consists of 10 parameters – 2 population parameters, 4 measurement error parameters, and 4 capture parameters. These parameters describe a population with two domains, each measured twice by two independent surveys. Both surveys have some coverage error. Although the ten parameters do not account for all situations, the framework is general enough for many realistic scenarios.

The two population parameters are:

- **N**: the size of the population.
- **P(T=O)**: the probability that an element in the population belongs to domain O.

The population is divided into two groups, O and V, where $P(T=O)$ represents the probability of being in group O and $P(T=V) = 1 - P(T=O)$ for group V. We use O and V as shorthand for “Occupied” and “Vacant,” although they could represent any binary classification. Additionally, T is a random variable denoting the true value.

There are four measurement parameters, two for each survey and two for each domain. The four parameters describing measurement error are:

- **P(X1=V|T=O)**: the probability that the first measurement classifies a unit as V given it belongs to O.
- **P(X1=O|T=V)**: the probability that the first measurement classifies a unit as O given it is in V.
- **P(X2=V|T=O)**: the probability that the second measurement classifies a unit as V given it belongs to O.
- **P(X2=O|T=V)**: the probability that the second measurement classifies a unit as O given it is V.

X1 and X2 are measurements collected for each element in N. Measurements are independent and conditional on the true value. Agreement rates are compliments of disagreement rates, (e.g., $P(X1=V|T=O) = 1 - P(X1=O|T=O)$).

There are also four capture parameters to account for coverage errors in both surveys. Two independent surveys seek to enumerate N. Both surveys have some coverage error, which may differ by domain and survey. In this framework, there are four additional parameters:

- **P(C=Y|T=O)** and **P(C=Y|T=V)** for the first survey (C stands for census).
- **P(P=Y|T=O)** and **P(P=Y|T=V)** for the second survey (P stands for PES).

In this context, C is a random variable that can take on the values N (not captured by the first survey) or Y (captured by the first survey). Likewise, P is a random variable that can take on the values N or Y for the second survey. Because an element in the population can either be captured or not, the non-capture rates are simply complements of the capture rates (e.g., $P(C=Y|T=O) = 1 - P(C=N|T=O)$).

Following assumptions from Otis et al. (1978) and Wolter (1986), we consider the Equal Catchability Model, the Petersen Model, and the Heterogeneity Model:

- **Equal Catchability Model**: Both surveys have the same capture rate, regardless of the group. That is, $P(C=Y|T=O) = P(C=Y|T=V) = P(P=Y|T=O) = P(P=Y|T=V)$.
- **Petersen Model**: Capture rates vary by survey, but not by domain. That is, $P(C=Y|T=O) = P(C=Y|T=V)$ and $P(P=Y|T=O) = P(P=Y|T=V)$.
- **Heterogeneity Model**: Capture rates vary by domain, but are the same across surveys. Thus, $P(C=Y|T=O) = P(P=Y|T=O)$ and $P(C=Y|T=V) = P(P=Y|T=V)$.

3.2.2 Simulation

To explore measurement error’s impact on dual-system estimation, we first used algebra to rewrite the DSE under the three capture models. Additionally, we simulated a population based on the ten

parameters, constructed confusion matrices, tabulated the DSE, and observed how the DSE responded to changes in measurement error and capture rates.

4. Results

4.1 Confusion Matrices

Confusion matrices displaying sample counts of disagreement between the 2020 Census and 2020 PES responses are provided in the appendix. To quantify the degree of disagreement between the two responses, we used the Aggregate Gross Difference Rate and the Aggregate Index of Inconsistency. Higher percentages indicate greater levels of disagreement. Previous census content reinterview studies categorized an index of inconsistency less than 20 as low, between 20 and 50 as moderate, and over 50 as high.

Table 2 presents the aggregate gross difference rate and aggregate index of inconsistency. According to labels from previous studies, we found that occupancy had a high aggregate index of inconsistency. Population count, tenure, American Indian or Alaska Native, Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander, and Some other Race had moderate aggregate indices of inconsistency. As eloquently stated in the 2000 Content Reinterview study:

“An aggregate index of zero means responses were in perfect agreement, but an index of 100 does not mean that all of the respondents changed answers. Rather, it means that we observed what we could expect if there were only chance agreement between original and reinterview answers.”

Table 2: Aggregate Gross Difference Rates and Aggregate Index of Inconsistency between 2020 Census and PES Characteristics

Characteristic	Aggregate Gross Difference Rate	Aggregate Index of Inconsistency
Pop Count	27.6%	39.1%
Tenure	16.9%	30.7%
Occupancy	7.8%	52.2%
Hispanic Origin	3.7%	12.5%
Race alone or in combination		
White	11.1%	27.0%
Black	2.5%	12.2%
Asian	2.3%	15.7%
American Indian or Alaska Native	3.1%	36.4%
Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	0.7%	31.2%
Some Other Race	9.9%	39.6%
Age-Sex (3 categories)	4.8%	7.4%
Age Sex (9) categories	13.4%	15.5%

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Appendix A contains the confusion matrices for the characteristics shown in Table 2. The E and P samples had different capture rates, as evidenced by differing numbers of E-sample nonmatches compared to P-sample nonmatches. In some tables, we see considerable counts in the off-diagonal

cells for the matches. This could be an indicator of measurement error. The Aggregate Gross Difference Rate quantifies the counts in the off-diagonal match cells as a percentage of the total cases. However, when comparing the off-diagonal cells to the smaller group, considerable differences were noted. For instance, in the tenure domain, the Aggregate Gross Difference Rate is 16.9%, but half of the matches classified as vacant in the census were labeled occupied in the PES.

4.2 Effect on DSE

To assess the impact of measurement error on the Dual-System Estimation (DSE), we used the framework described earlier to rewrite the DSE under the Equal Catchability, Petersen, and Heterogeneity models. The supporting algebra for these results is detailed in Appendix B.

4.2.1 Equal Catchability and Petersen Models

For the O domain, the DSE under the Equal Catchability and Petersen models can be expressed as:

$$\overline{DSE}_O = N * [P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O)] + N * [P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V)]$$

That is, the DSE under these models simplifies to the sum of occupied units correctly classified by the census and the vacant units misclassified by the census.

The true population size can be expressed as:

$$No = N * [P(T=O) * (P(X1=O|T=O))] + N * [P(T=O) * (P(X1=V|T=O))]$$

Subtracting these two gives us the bias of the DSE:

$$\text{Bias}(\overline{DSE}_O) = N * [P(T=O) * P(X1=V|T=O)] - N * [P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V)]$$

The first term represents the number of true O units misclassified as V, while the second term represents the number of true Va units classified as O by the census.

Thus, if more O units are misclassified as V than V units misclassified as O, the bias will be positive. Conversely, if fewer O units are misclassified as V than V units misclassified as O, the bias will be negative. And, if the number of misclassified units is balanced, the DSE will be unbiased. That is, if the number of O units that the census misclassified as V is equal to the number of V units that the census misclassifies as O, \overline{DSE}_O will be unbiased.

This formula shows that dual-system estimates can be biased if misclassification rates are equal. For instance, if $P(X1=V|T=O) = P(X1=O|T=V)$, bias arises if the two groups are not of equal size. Consider the situation where the census misclassifies 1% of all occupied and vacant units. If 90% of the housing units are occupied and 10% are vacant, the DSE for occupied units will be about 1% lower than the true value and the DSE for vacant units will be about 8% higher than the true value. Hence, a small misclassification rate in a large domain can substantially skew the DSE for a small domain, even when the two surveys (or captures) are independent and the strict assumptions of the Equal Catchability and Petersen Models are not violated.

4.2.2 Heterogeneity Capture Model

The Heterogeneity Capture model allows for capture rates to vary by domain but not across survey. That is,

1. $P(C=Y|T=O) = P(P=Y|T=O) = p_o$ and
2. $P(C=Y|T=V) = P(P=Y|T=V) = p_v$

This model is more realistic than the Equal Catchability and Petersen models because historic data show that census coverage varies across demographic groups and by housing unit characteristics. However, fewer terms cancel in the algebra; so the DSE formulas are not as elegant or easy to interpret as the Equal Catchability and Petersen models. Under the Heterogeneity Capture Model,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{DSE}_O &= N * [P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * p_o + P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * p_v] * \\ &\quad [P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p_o + P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p_v] / \\ &\quad \{[P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p_o * p_o] + [P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p_v * p_v]\} \end{aligned}$$

We conducted simulations to explore the bias of DSE_O under this model. We examined three scenarios based on measurement error:

1. Constant measurement error: $P(X1=V|T=O) = P(X1=O|T=V) = P(X2=V|T=O) = P(X2=O|T=V) = m$.
2. Constant measurement error by domain: $P(X1=V|T=O) = P(X2=V|T=O) = m_o$ and $P(X1=O|T=V) = P(X2=O|T=V) = m_v$.
3. Constant measurement error within survey: $P(X1=V|T=O) = P(X1=O|T=V) = m_1$, and $P(X2=V|T=O) = P(X2=O|T=V) = m_2$.

Table 3 shows the bias of DSE_O, DSE_V, and DSE under these scenarios using the following parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= 100 \\
 p(T=O) &= 0.9 \text{ and } p(T=V) = 0.1 \\
 p(C=Y|T=O) &= 0.8 \text{ and } P(C=N|T=O) = 0.2 \\
 p(P=Y|T=O) &= 0.8 \text{ and } P(P=N|T=O) = 0.2 \\
 p(C=Y|T=V) &= 0.7 \text{ and } P(C=N|T=V) = 0.2 \\
 p(P=Y|T=V) &= 0.7 \text{ and } P(P=N|T=V) = 0.2
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the true population has 90 occupied units and 10 vacant units. Both surveys capture 80% of the occupied units and 70% of the vacant units.

Cases 1 and 2 depict the equal measurement error situation, with Case 1 having 5% measurement error and Case 2 having 20% measurement error. Cases 3 and 4 depict the situation where measurement error depends on the domain, but not by survey – so occupied units have one measurement error and vacant units have a different measurement error rate. Cases 5 and 6 show the situation where measurement error varies by survey. Lastly, Case 7 shows a situation where the measurement error of occupied units in the first survey is smaller than the other measurement errors.

Table 3: Bias for Domain Dual-System Estimates (DSEs) for Seven Different Simulations

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7
$P(X1=V T=O)$	5%	20%	5%	20%	20%	5%	5%
$P(X1=O T=V)$	5%	20%	20%	5%	20%	5%	20%
$P(X2=V T=O)$	5%	20%	5%	20%	5%	20%	20%
$P(X2=O T=V)$	5%	20%	20%	5%	5%	20%	20%
Bias of DSE _O	-4	-16	-3	-18	-16	-4	-2
Bias of DSE _V	4	16	2	17	17	3	2
Bias of DSE	0	0	0	0	1	-1	-1

This table does not show all possible scenarios, but among the situations considered, the bias of DSE_O is smallest in Cases 1, 3, 6, and 7. In all four of these situations, $P(X1=V|T=O)$ is small, indicating that accurate classification of larger domains in the first survey is crucial. From this table, we conjecture that survey designers should focus on accurate classification of the bigger domains in the first survey. Interestingly, this guidance also yields the smallest bias of DSE_V. The second conclusion from this table is that even modest magnitudes of measurement error can have a relatively large impact on small groups. Under the parameters in this simulation, there are 10 vacant units. Even the cases with the smallest bias of DSE_V (Cases 3 and 7) results in a bias of 2, meaning a 20% overestimate of the number of 10 vacant units.

Appendix C includes plots showing the bias of the DSE as measurement error changes under each scenario, using the same parameters as the table.

- **Figure 1:** Shows the relationship between measurement error and bias when it does not vary by survey or domain, with bias increasing negatively as measurement error increases.
- **Figures 2 and 3:** Show measurement error dependent on domain, DSE_O understating the true value by greater and greater amounts as the measurement error of O increases. Figures

2 and 3 suggest that we generally should seek to minimize the measurement error for the domain of interest. The fact that the four lines in figure 2 are nearly overlapping suggest that the measurement error in the domain of interest is a driver of the bias for the larger domain. Figure 3 shows how measurement error in the other domain can impact bias. For a fixed amount of measurement error in O, bias of DSE_O can be reduced by increasing measurement error in V so that it offsets the measurement error in O. So, the general takeaway, is that we want to minimize the measurement error of our domain of interest. However, if we have measurement error in O, bias of DSE_O can be reduced by adding enough measurement error in V to offset the measurement error in O.

- **Figures 4 and 5:** Show the impact of different measurement error rates by survey but not domain. From Figure 4, the overlapping lines suggest that the bias does not depend on measurement error in the second survey. As measurement error in the first survey increases, the bias of DSE_O increases in the negative direction. Figure 5 shows that the bias of DSE_O is fairly small if the measurement error of the first survey is small. Additionally, the bias of DSE_O is fairly constant unless the measurement error in the second survey exceeds about 60%.

5. Discussion

5.1 Prevalence of Misclassification

Evidence suggests that housing unit and demographic characteristics were measured differently between the census and PES. Without access to the true values, it's impossible to definitively determine the accuracy and precision of these estimates. However, the lack of symmetry in the off-diagonal cells for matched records indicates that at least one of the measurements may be systematically favoring one classification. Although the gross difference rates and index of inconsistency align with previous content reinterview studies, there is still room for improvement.

Future studies could apply statistical tests of independence to determine if the two measurements are independent of each other. A more in-depth analysis of the confusion matrices might yield further insights. Measures such as Cronbach's Alpha and chi-squared tests might help describe the degree of misclassification. Additionally, future work could aim to use the two measurements to make inference about the "true" values. Latent class models or other models may prove helpful in this regard.

5.2 Effect of Misclassification

Dual-system estimates are particularly sensitive to disagreement between reported characteristics and the "true" values. Figures in Appendix show points where there is measurement error, yet DSE_O remains unbiased. While we did not explore a formula to pinpoint where the errors offset each other in this study, future research could investigate the conditions for unbiased DSE_O , DSE_V , and DSE . Under the Equal Catchability and Petersen models, these estimates are unbiased when the confusion matrix is symmetric.

We recommend focusing on accurate measurement of large groups in the first survey, contributing to the DSE numerator. Future research could explore strategies to minimize measurement error's impact on DSE, including recent work by Van Der Heijden (2022) and Hwang et al. (2003 and 2007).

In this study, we fixed population parameters and capture rates. It would be interesting to see how different capture rates and domain sizes effect the results. Although we used common capture rate models, we didn't address measurement error when capture rates vary by survey and domain. Future research could explore this more flexible model, as it is likely to occur in practice for post-enumeration surveys.

While our framework for exploring dual-system estimation with error is robust, there are opportunities for greater flexibility. In practice, some units may be harder to measure accurately

than others. Extending the model to accommodate varying measurement error rates across different subsets of domains could refine our analysis. Adding parameters for erroneous inclusions in either system would make these results more applicable to dual-system estimation with administrative records, which often have some erroneous inclusions.

This paper dealt with dichotomous domains. Another extension of this paper would be to extend the framework and results to an arbitrary number of domains as well as for logistic regression based estimators.

Lastly, the two parts of this project used different ways to express measurement error: prevalence measures used gross difference rates and the index of inconsistency, while the effect of misclassification used probabilities of measurement error. A more integrated approach that combines reported data into sensitivity analyses might advance our understanding of the plausible range of DSEs with measurement error estimates.

6. Conclusion

Repeated measurements, even of objective and factual characteristics such as the housing unit occupancy, often disagree. This paper found evidence of such disagreement between Census and PES measurements of housing unit and demographic characteristics. We developed a straightforward framework to explore how measurement error impacts dual-system estimates of domains. We found that disagreement in measurements can substantially impact dual-system estimates, especially for less prevalent groups.

Our research highlights the importance of accurately measuring the largest domains in the first survey. Future surveys should focus on this to improve dual-system estimates of domains.

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Appendix A

Table A1: Confusion Matrix for Household Size Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status					Total
		Zero	One	Two	Three +	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Zero	6,200	2,300	2,200	1,700	3,900	16,500
	One	2,200	26,000	4,900	2,800	7,000	43,000
	Two	1,600	5,000	31,000	5,400	6,700	50,000
	Three	1,500	4,500	6,100	42,000	7,300	61,500
Not in E-sample		2,000	1,300	1,000	1,200		
Total		13,500	39,000	45,500	53,000		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A2: Confusion Matrix for Tenure Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status				Total
		Owned	Rented	Vacant	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Owned	72,000	6,500	2,300	10,000	90,800
	Rented	6,700	42,500	2,900	11,000	63,100
	Vacant	3,100	3,100	6,200	3,900	16,300
	Not in E-sample	1,800	1,700	2,000		
Total		83,600	53,800	13,400		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A3: Confusion Matrix for Tenure Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Occupied	Vacant	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Occupied	127,700	5,200	21,000	153,900
	Vacant	6,200	6,200	3,900	16,300
	Not in E-sample	3,500	2,000		
Total		137,400	13,400		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A4: Confusion Matrix for Hispanic Origin Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Not Hispanic	Hispanic	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Not Hispanic	202,000	4,100	44,500	251,000
	Hispanic	5,200	40,500	12,500	58,500
	Not in E-sample	27,500	8,300		
Total		235,000	53,000		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A5: Confusion Matrix for White Alone or in Combination Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Not White	White	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Not White	59,000	16,000	23,500	98,500
	White	12,000	165,000	33,500	211,000
	Not in E-sample	14,500	21,500		
Total		85,500	203,000		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A6: Confusion Matrix for Black Alone or in Combination Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Not Black	Black	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Not Black	219,000	2,600	46,500	269,000
	Black	3,800	26,500	10,500	41,000
	Not in E-sample	29,500	6,200		
Total		253,000	35,500		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A7: Confusion Matrix for Asian Alone or in Combination Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Not Asian	Asian	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Not Asian	229,000	2,000	52,000	283,000
	Asian	3,900	17,500	5,000	26,500
	Not in E-sample	33,000	2,600		
Total		266,000	22,500		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A8: Confusion Matrix for American Indian or Alaska Native (AIAN) Alone or in Combination Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Not AIAN	AIAN	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Not AIAN	237,000	2,700	52,000	292,000
	AIAN	5,200	7,400	5,000	17,500
	Not in E-sample	33,000	2,600		
Total		275,000	13,000		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A9: Confusion Matrix for Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander (NHPI) Alone or in Combination Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Not NHPI	NHPI	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Not NHPI	249,000	700	56,000	306,000
	NHPI	1,000	1,900	850	3,800
	Not in E-sample	35,500	450		
Total		286,000	3,000		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A10: Confusion Matrix for Some Other Race (SOR) Alone or in Combination Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status			Total
		Not SOR	SOR	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Not SOR	203,000	13,000	47,000	263,000
	SOR	12,000	24,500	9,800	46,500
	Not in E-sample	29,000	6,800		
Total		244,000	44,500		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A11: Confusion Matrix for Broad Age/Sex Groups Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status				Total
		Child 0-17	Male 18+	Female 18+	Not in P-sample	
E-sample status	Child 0-17	51,000	1,900	1,800	15,500	70,500
	Male 18+	2,100	90,500	2,100	20,000	115,000
	Female 18+	2,100	2,100	99,000	21,500	124,000
	Not in E-sample	8,300	14,000	13,500		
Total		63,500	109,000	116,000		

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Table A12: Confusion Matrix for Detailed Age/Sex Groups Between Matched and Nonmatched P-Sample and E-Sample Housing Units

		P-sample status										Total
		0-4	5 to 9	10 to 17	18-29 Male	18-29 Female	30-49 Male	30-49 Female	50+ Male	50+ Female	Not in P sample	
E Sample Status	0 to 4	11,000	700	600	200	200	100	100	60	60	4,300	17,500
	5 to 9	700	12,500	1,000	250	250	100	100	70	60	4,300	19,500
	10 to 17	700	1,000	22,500	700	600	250	250	150	150	7,000	33,500
	18-29 Male	250	250	600	13,500	300	950	70	650	80	5,500	22,000
	18-29 Female	250	250	500	300	13,500	80	1,000	90	700	5,500	22,000
	30-49 Male	150	150	350	1,100	90	27,000	400	2,400	200	7,100	39,000
	30-49 Female	150	200	300	100	1,100	400	29,000	200	2,600	7,200	41,000
	50+ Male	100	100	200	750	70	2,400	150	41,500	700	7,200	53,000
	50+ Female	100	100	250	70	850	100	2,500	700	47,500	8,800	61,000
	Not in E Sample	2,400	2,300	3,600	4,100	3,700	5,000	4,500	5,000	5,100		
Total	16,000	18,000	30,000	21,000	20,500	36,500	38,000	50,500	57,500			

Notes: This table does not include P-sample housing unit matches to census enumerations that were excluded from the E sample. We also excluded addresses that were part of the field data collection, but that were later determined to not be eligible for the P sample. This table represents the P and E samples for the United States only.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, Decennial Statistical Studies Division, 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey (October 2024 Release).

Appendix B

B.1 Notation

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{ooo} &= N_{ooo} * P(C=Y|T=O) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) \\
C_{oov} &= N_{oov} * P(C=Y|T=O) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=V|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) \\
C_{voo} &= N_{voo} * P(C=Y|T=V) \\
&= N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) \\
C_{vov} &= N_{vov} * P(C=Y|T=V) \\
&= N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=V|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) \\
M_{ooo} &= N_{ooo} * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
M_{oov} &= N_{oov} * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=V|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
M_{voo} &= N_{voo} * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
&= N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
M_{vov} &= N_{vov} * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
&= N * P(T=V) * P(X1=V|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
P_{ooo} &= N_{ooo} * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
P_{oov} &= N_{oov} * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=V|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) \\
P_{voo} &= N_{voo} * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
&= N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
P_{vov} &= N_{vov} * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
&= N * P(T=V) * P(X1=V|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)
\end{aligned}$$

B.2 DSE

$$\begin{aligned}
DSE_{occ} &= (C_{ooo} + C_{oov} + C_{voo} + C_{vov}) (P_{ooo} + P_{oov} + P_{voo} + P_{vov}) / (M_{ooo} + M_{oov} + M_{voo} + M_{vov}) \\
&= \frac{[N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) + N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V)] * [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)]}{[N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)]}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&(C_{ooo} + C_{oov} + C_{voo} + C_{vov}) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) + \\
&\quad N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=V|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) + \\
&\quad N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) + \\
&\quad N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=V|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * [P(X2=O|T=O) + P(X2=V|T=O)] + \\
&\quad N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * [P(X2=O|T=V) + P(X2=V|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

Since $P(X2=O|T=O)$ and $P(X2=V|T=O)$ are mutually exclusive and exhaustive, they sum to 1.

Likewise $P(X2=O|T=V) + P(X2=V|T=V) = 1$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) + \\
&\quad N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&(M_{ooo} + M_{oov} + M_{voo} + M_{vov}) \\
&= N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
&\quad N * P(T=O) * P(X1=V|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
&\quad N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& N * P(T=V) * P(X1=V|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
= & N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) * P(X1=V|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) * P(X1=V|T=V) \\
= & N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) * \\
& [P(X1=O|T=O) + P(X1=V|T=O)] + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) * \\
& [P(X1=O|T=V) + P(X1=V|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

Since $P(X1=O|T=O)$ and $P(X1=V|T=O)$ are mutually exclusive and exhaustive, they sum to 1.

Likewise $P(X1=O|T=V) + P(X1=V|T=V) = 1$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
= & N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)
\end{aligned}$$

$$(P_{ooo} + P_{ovo} + P_{voo} + P_{vvo})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
= & N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=O) * P(X1=V|T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X1=V|T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) \\
= & N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) * [P(X1=O|T=O) + P(X1=V|T=O)] + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V) * [P(X1=O|T=V) + P(X1=V|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

Since $P(X1=O|T=O)$ and $P(X1=V|T=O)$ are mutually exclusive and exhaustive, they sum to 1.

Likewise $P(X1=O|T=V) + P(X1=V|T=V) = 1$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
= & N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)
\end{aligned}$$

B.3 Equal Catchability Model

$$DSE_{occ}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
= & [N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V)] * \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)] / \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

Under equal catchability, $P(C=Y|T=O) = P(P=Y|T=O) = P(C=Y|T=V) = P(P=Y|T=V) = p$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
= & [N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * p + N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * p] * \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p] / \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p * p + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p * p] \\
= & N * p * [P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V)] * \\
& N * p * [P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V)] \setminus \\
& \{N * p^2 * [P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V)]\} \\
= & N * [P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

B.4 Petersen Model

$$DSE_{occ}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
= & [N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V)] * \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)] / \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

Under Peterson Model, $P(C=Y|T=O) = P(C=Y|T=V) = p_c$ and $P(P=Y|T=O) = P(P=Y|T=V) = p_p$.

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
= & [N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * p_c + N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * p_c] * \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p_p + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p_p] /
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p_c * p_p + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p_c * p_p] \\
= & N * p_c * [P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V)] * \\
& N * p_p * [P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) + [P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V)]] / \\
= & \{N * p_c * p_p * [P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V)]\} \\
& N * [P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

B.5 Heterogeneity Model

DSE_{occ}

$$\begin{aligned}
= & [N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V)] * \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)] / \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * P(C=Y|T=O) * P(P=Y|T=O) + \\
& N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * P(C=Y|T=V) * P(P=Y|T=V)]
\end{aligned}$$

Under Heterogeneity Model, $P(C=Y|T=O) = P(P=Y|T=O) = p_o$ and $P(C=Y|T=V) = P(P=Y|T=V) = p_v$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
= & [N * P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) * p_o + N * P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V) * p_v] * \\
& [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p_o + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p_v] / \\
= & [N * P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) * p_o * p_o + N * P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V) * p_v * p_v] \\
& N * p_c * [P(T=O) * P(X1=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X1=O|T=V)] * \\
& N * p_p * [P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) + [P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V)]] / \\
& \{N * p_c * p_p * [P(T=O) * P(X2=O|T=O) + P(T=V) * P(X2=O|T=V)]\}
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix C

Figure 1: Relationship between measurement error and bias when it does not vary by survey or domain. Bias increases negatively as measurement error increases.

Figure 2: Relationship between measurement error and bias of DSE_O when measurement errors vary by true value, but not across survey. X-axis shows $P(X1=V|T=O)$. Line color corresponds to fixed values of $P(X1=O|T=V)$. Blue line shows $P(X1=O|T=V) = 0.25$, green line shows $P(X1=O|T=V) = 0.10$, yellow line shows $P(X1=O|T=V) = 0.05$, and red line shows $P(X1=O|T=V) = 0.01$.

Figure 3: Relationship between measurement error and bias of DSEo when measurement errors vary by true value, but not across survey. X-axis shows $P(X1=O|T=V)$. Line color corresponds to fixed values of $P(X1=V|T=O)$. Blue line shows $P(X1=V|T=O) = 0.25$, green line shows $P(X1=V|T=O) = 0.10$, yellow line shows $P(X1=V|T=O) = 0.05$, and red line shows $P(X1=V|T=O) = 0.01$.

Figure 4: Relationship between measurement error and bias of DSEo when measurement errors vary across survey, but not by true value. X-axis shows $P(X1=V|T=O)$. Line color corresponds to fixed values of $P(X2=V|T=O)$. Blue line shows $P(X2=V|T=O) = 0.25$, green line shows $P(X2=V|T=O) = 0.10$, yellow line shows $P(X2=V|T=O) = 0.05$, and red line shows $P(X2=V|T=O) = 0.01$.

Figure 5: Relationship between measurement error and bias of DSEo when measurement errors vary across survey, but not by true value. X-axis shows $P(X_2=V|T=O)$. Line color corresponds to fixed values of $P(X_1=V|T=O)$. Blue line shows $P(X_1=V|T=O) = 0.25$, green line shows $P(X_1=V|T=O) = 0.10$, yellow line shows $P(X_1=V|T=O) = 0.05$, and red line shows $P(X_1=V|T=O) = 0.01$.